

RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DENTAL DISEASES IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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Abstract. *Pregnancy is a physiological process makes a woman's body more demanding of all types of metabolism, which leads to a change in the environment of the body, in particular blood and saliva. Deeper changes in metabolic processes occur during the pathological course of pregnancy. From the data literature is aware of the relationship between obstetric pathology and the nature of changes in the oral cavity of a pregnant woman Studies conducted in our country and abroad have shown a close relationship between dental diseases in women and the nature of the course of pregnancy The fact of an increase in the frequency and severity of the pathology of hard tissues of teeth, periodontal tissues, mucous membranes of the oral cavity in the pathological course of pregnancy is not raises doubts.*

Keywords: *Hygiene, biochemical parameters, pregnant women, pH.*

ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА РАЗВИТИЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН

Аннотация. *Беременность - это физиологический процесс, который делает организм женщины более требовательным ко всем видам обмена веществ, что приводит к изменению окружающей среды организма, в частности крови и слюны. Более глубокие изменения в обменных процессах происходят во время патологического течения беременности. Из данных литературы известно о взаимосвязи между акушерской патологией и характером изменений в полости рта беременной женщины Исследования проведенные в нашей стране и за рубежом показали тесную взаимосвязь между стоматологическими заболеваниями у женщин и характером течения беременности Фактом увеличения частоты и тяжести наличие патологии твердых тканей зубов, тканей пародонта, слизистых оболочек полости рта при патологическом течении беременности не вызывает сомнений.*

Ключевые слова: *Гигиена, биохимические показатели, беременные женщины, фотография.*

The most important factors reflecting specific functions of the female body and providing direct influence on the occurrence of iron deficiency anemia, are profuse and prolonged menstruation, gynecological and extragenital diseases before pregnancy, anemia during past pregnancies, frequent pregnancies, recurring before 2- 3 years, pregnancy during lactation, pregnancy in the teenage period.

Menstrual dysfunctions, which are mainly of a functional nature, were more common in 16.3% of the examined women of the first group, in 11.2% of women in the second and 11.26% of the third groups, which probably contributed to the development iron deficiency anemia in pregnant women Late menarche was found in 19.6% of women of the first group In the second and third groups - respectively in 14.2 and 13.9% of cases Late onset of menstruation indicates, according to the literature, a violation of hormonal balance in the body of women during puberty Abundant menstrual bleeding is a risk factor for iron deficiency anemia.

In the first group of observations, heavy menstruation was registered in 34.2%, in the second and third groups, the figures are slightly lower - 20.5 and 21.3% respectively.

It should be noted that 38.5% of women in the first and 18.12% of the second groups pointed out anemia in the past, linking it to previous pregnancies and childbirth. Moreover, in 12.3% of women in the first group, the present pregnancy occurred against the background of untreated iron deficiency anemia.

According to the severity of iron deficiency anemia (according to the classification of L.I. Idelson, 1981), in women of the first group, anemia of the 1st degree of severity was noted in 79.3% of cases, of the 2nd degree of severity – in 20.1%, 3rd severity was not found

An analysis of the data obtained indicates that iron deficiency anemia during pregnancy is a consequence of latent or chronic iron deficiency anemia detected even before pregnancy.

The results of the survey of pregnant women did not reveal significant differences in the answers in both the first and second groups, therefore survey data are presented as general results. It was revealed that pregnant women did not have knowledge of the rules of rational nutrition during pregnancy. In 56.7±2.75% of pregnant women bread and potatoes prevailed in the diet. Pregnant women consumed a lot of sweets 36.8±2.68%. Of these products, bakery and confectionery products accounted for 69.5±2.56%. Rigid vegetables and fruits never consumed at the end of a meal 44.7±2.76%.

Hygiene measures for the oral cavity were regularly carried out by 71.62±2.7% of women, irregularly by 23.0±2.34%. The results of the survey showed that only 39.6±2.72% of women use additional objects and means of oral care. At the same time, toothpicks were used most often by 52.3 ± threads (flosses) - 38.4±4.3%, less often - elixirs - 9.3±2.57%.

The reliability of the answers is supported by the results of a dental examination, which was carried out in parallel with the questionnaire. Pregnant women showed a poor level of hygiene according to Green-Vermillion - 2.44±1.13 in the first group and 2.16±1.09 in the first group.

Thus, most pregnant women, regardless on the nature of the course of pregnancy, there is no knowledge about rational nutrition, skills and regularity of oral care, and this may be a risk factor for the development of dental diseases.

Biochemical parameters of mixed saliva of women with different pregnancy.

It has been established that with the onset of pregnancy in the body of women (groups 1 and 2), significant changes in mineral and protein metabolism occur in comparison with non-pregnant women (group 3).

The results of the study of mineral metabolism showed that in women of the first and second groups compared with women of the third group, there is a significant decrease in total calcium in mixed saliva - 0.820 + 0.03 mmol / l (group 1), 1.09±0.03 mmol / l (2nd group), 1.30±0.04 mmol/l (3rd group).

Analysis of the content of total calcium in the age aspect revealed its maximum decrease at the age of 18–20 years in all groups of examined women.

Analysis of the mineralizing potential of the saliva of the examined women showed that in the first group, the 3rd type of crystallization prevailed - 44.5±4.4%, in the second and third - the 1st type - 42.86±6.8 and 67.5±7.4%.

In the 3rd type of saliva crystallization, a violation of the crystal structure was noted. In the 1st and 2nd types, the crystal structure, although differed, but at the same time retained its clarity.

When studying the protein content in saliva, some its decrease in the first group was 1.58 g/l, which may be the result of the restructuring of the protein metabolism of women during pregnancy and the increased use of protein by the growing fetus.

In the age aspect, the smallest amount of protein in the first group of the examined was found at the age of 18-20 years - 1.57 ± 0.01 g/l, during the second and third groups - at the age of 26-30 years, respectively 1.61 ± 0.01 g/l, 1.65 ± 0.01 g/l.

Indicators of mineral and protein metabolism are quite clear characterize the direction to reduce the amount of total calcium and total protein in mixed saliva, increase the intensity caries in pregnant women with iron deficiency anemia. Studies of the concentration of hydrogen ions in mixed saliva showed that in women of the third group, the pH was within neutral border 7.11, in women of the second group - it was observed acidification of saliva to 6.7, in the first group this figure was still lower and amounted to 6.2.

In terms of age, the lowest pH was found in women aged 18–20 in all groups examined.

The correlation analysis carried out made it possible to identify significant positive relationships between the intensity of dental caries and biochemical composition of mixed saliva with mineralizing potential $r = 0.74$, Ca $r = 0.69$, pH $r = 0.63$, protein $r = 0.63$ ($p < 0.001$).

Therefore, during pregnancy in the body of a woman against the background iron deficiency anemia, there are changes in the mineral and protein metabolism, leading to a decrease in the content of total calcium, total protein in mixed saliva and a shift in pH to the acid side.

Thus, in pregnant women with iron deficiency anemia revealed a decrease in the content of total calcium, total protein and pH in mixed saliva, which manifested itself in an increase in the prevalence and intensity of dental caries, the incidence of periodontal tissues, oral mucosa.

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